

USE OF MODERN TECHNOLOGIES IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING METHODS

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Annotation: It is no secret that our President is currently implementing a variety of changes to encourage the study of foreign languages, particularly English. As a result, the author covers the necessity of learning other languages in depth in this essay, as well as the methodology of learning English and the ability to employ new technologies in the process of language instruction.

Keywords: Foreign language, game, innovative technology, technological tools, methods, techniques and etc.

Foreign language skills are now an essential aspect of vocational training. Specialists in numerous sectors collaborate extensively with overseas partners, resulting in a significant need for learning. Foreign languages are becoming an increasingly important aspect of occupational training in today's culture. People first gain such knowledge at schools, colleges, and lyceums, and then in institutions, training courses, or by being acquainted with basic information sets that let them learn a foreign language independently. There is a huge array of educational resources available today for people with varying degrees of language proficiency. The success of this goal is dependent on the wise approaches and skills of teachers.

The ability to use information technology and modern teaching methods aids in the rapid acquisition of new material. A teacher can solve certain courses by combining diverse strategies. In this regard, teachers and students learned about modern ways of teaching foreign languages. As a consequence, you will be able to select the most effective method for achieving your objectives. It is possible to be effective while using a range of teaching and learning strategies. Teaching occurs in

incremental increments and is based on the student's pre-existing knowledge system. The emphasis at this stage is on pronunciation. The first prerequisite of a native speaker, according to Harmer, is pronunciation.

The teacher should specialize in the student's pronunciation from the start of the training procedure. Grammar and vocabulary are vital, but they are meaningless if the speaker mispronounces them. Native speakers can understand grammatical faults in speech if the speaker pronounces the words appropriately. As a result, the emphasis in instruction is on pronunciation. The use of various audios from native speakers yields good results in this scenario. During the lecture, the teacher should demonstrate proper letter and word pronunciation. Early on, there is also a strong emphasis on speech and reading skills. When it comes to sorts of speaking activities in foreign language instruction, the following tasks should be completed:

- Create a reading mechanism;
- Improving oral reading techniques;
- Teach them to know what they're reading.

The emphasis in the Elementary level is on reading aloud. Reading texts is also becoming more straightforward. However, it should be emphasized that, while the first stage of the add is particularly focused on the event of oral abilities, it does not address the issue of developing oral communication in English. She is only getting ready to work on a formal speech. Furthermore, reading words attractively and fluently boosts a student's enthusiasm for studying the language. Furthermore, pupils will be introduced to this indefinite Tense, The Past indefinite Tense. It is necessary to be acquainted with verb tenses such as the Future indefinite Tense and to be able to employ verb forms vividly in these tenses.

Independent work, particularly in foreign languages, plays an important role at the upper level. Of course, the prerequisites for this course differ from those for earlier ones. And because the lesson is no longer based on oral communication, much of the linguistic material is studied passively at this stage (receptively). That is, reading comprehension is essential. Texts are also vast in size, and language

materials are difficult to understand. Reading, speaking, and listening exercises are held on a regular basis. When planning a lesson, a separate day is put aside for reading, another for speaking, and yet another for listening. Homework is also more difficult than the previous phases. Speaking lessons consist of a topic and a two-minute presentation. Students will also be given text cards as an alternative. On the card of their choice, each student expresses their thoughts on the issue. The speech necessitates the employment of previously heard phrases, introductory words, new words, and synonyms. Homework can be utilized to prepare new text topics by researching them in the press, journals, media, and internet. Students will be interested in learning about exciting scientific studies and discoveries.

The demand for studying a foreign language is increasing on a daily and incremental basis. As previously said, foreign language is split into four components (reading, reading, listening comprehension, and speaking), each of which provides distinct concepts and skills. Educational technology is a powerful tool of modern information technology that can be used in the educational process. It will also attempt to increase the quality and efficacy of education by incorporating current innovative technologies into the educational process. There are various advantages to using such information and communication technology in learning foreign languages in particular.

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